
Renal Involvement in COVID-19 Patients

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a critical complication of COVID19, associated with high morbidity and mortality. Data from low resource settings remain scarce.

Objective:To determine the frequency, risk factors, treatment modalities, and outcomes of AKI among hospitalized COVID19 patients in Khartoum,Sudan

Methods:A multicenter crosssectional study was conducted from September to December 2021. Data from 170 hospitalized COVID-19 patients were analyzed using SPSS. AKI was defined and staged using KDIGO criteria.

Results:The frequency of AKI was 66.5% (113/170). Among AKI patients, 69% required renal replacement therapy (RRT), with 51.3% receiving continuous RRT and 48.7% intermittent hemodialysis. Significant predictors of AKI included sepsis (p=0.001) and hemodynamic instability (p=0.001). Mortality was significantly higher in AKI patients (57.5% vs. 31.6%, p=0.001). Comorbidities showed a non-significant trend toward AKI.

Conclusion:

AKI is highly prevalent among severe COVID19 patients in Sudan and is associated with markedly increased mortality. Early screening, prompt management of sepsis and hemodynamic instability, and preparedness for RRT are essential in improving outcomes

KEYWORDS: Acute kidney injury, COVID-19, Sudan.

INTRODUCTION

The SARS_CoV2 pandemic has revealed multiorgan involvement, with acute kidney injury (AKI) emerging as a frequent and serious complication among hospitalized patients.[1] AKI in COVID19 is associated with prolonged hospitalization, increased need for critical care, and high mortality rates.[2,3] The pathophysiology involves direct viral cytopathy via ACE2 receptors, cytokine storm, endothelial dysfunction, hypercoagulability, and hemodynamic instability.[4,5] Despite global reports, data from sub-Saharan Africa, particularly Sudan, are limited. This study aims to elucidate the risk factors, modalities of renal replacement therapy (RRT), clinical outcomes, and management strategies for AKI in COVID-19 patients in Khartoum, Sudan.

EPIDEMIOLOGY AND RISK FACTORS

Global prevalence of AKI in COVID_19 varies widely (5_46%), influenced by demographics, comorbidities, and illness severity. [6,7] Advanced age, male gender, hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and chronic kidney disease are established risk factors.

[8,9] The Sudanese population presents a unique profile with high burdens of hypertension and diabetes, potentially amplifying AKI risk.[10].

RENAL REPLACEMENT THERAPY

Approximately 20_30% of COVID_19 AKI patients require RRT.[14] Modalities include continuous RRT (CRRT) and intermittent hemodialysis (IHD). CRRT is often preferred in hemodynamically unstable patients, though resource constraints in low-income settings limit its availability. [15] Outcomes are influenced by timing, modality, and comorbidities.

Mortality and Outcomes

AKI significantly increases mortality in COVID_19, with reported odds ratios as high as 23.9.[16] Even mild AKI (Stage 1) elevates risk. Survivors often experience incomplete renal recovery, leading to chronic kidney disease.[17,18]

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Guidelines and Management

KDIGO guidelines recommend early detection using serum creatinine and urine output, avoidance of nephrotoxins, and timely RR T.[19] In COVID-19, additional emphasis is placed on managing hyperinflammation and thrombosis.[20]

DATA COLLECTION & METHODS

Study Design and Setting

A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted at three hospitals in Khartoum from September to December 2021.

Included: Adults (≥ 18 years) hospitalized with PCR-confirmed COVID-19.

Excluded: pre-existing end-stage renal disease on dialysis.

Demographic, clinical, laboratory, and outcome data were extracted using a structured form. AKI was defined and staged using K DIGO criteria.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data analyzed using SPSS v25.0. Chi-square and t-tests were used for associations. P-value < 0.05 was significant.

RESULTS

DEMOGRAPHICS AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Among 170 patients, nearly two-thirds (66.5%) were above 60 years of age (Figure 1), with a male predominance of 62.9% (male : female ratio 1.7:1; Figure 2). The median hospital stay was 1-

7 days for 39.4% of patients, while 32.4% stayed for more than 14 days (Figure 3). Common isolated comorbidities included hypertension (6.7%), diabetes mellitus (12.9%), and cardiovascular disease (1.2%) (Figure 4).

Figure 1. Age distribution of the study participants (n=170).

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Figure 2. Gender distribution of the study participants (n=170).

Figure 3. Length of hospital stay among the participants (n=170).

Figure 4. Distribution of comorbidities among the participants (n=170).

CLINICAL COURSE AND INTERVENTIONS

Nearly half (47.6%) of participants required supplemental oxygen, primarily via non rebreather masks (67.9%). Most patients (64.1%) required mechanical ventilation, with the invasive type being predominant (72.5 %) (Tables 1 & 2). The most common complications post_admission were sepsis (68.8%) and hemodynamic instability (42.9%) (Table 3). Only 10% of patients received nephrotoxic medications (Figure 5).

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Table 1. Oxygen requirement among participants (n=170).

Oxygen requirement	Frequency	Percent %
Yes	81	47.6
No	89	52.4
Type (n=81)		
-nasal cannula	17	21.0
-Simple Face Mask	18	22.2
-Non-Rebreather Mask	55	67.9

Table 2. Mechanical ventilator requirement among participants (n=170).

Mechanical ventilator requirement	Frequency	Percent %
Yes	109	64.1
No	61	35.9
Type (n=109)		
-Invasive	79	72.5
-Non-Invasive	30	27.5

Table 3. Problems developed after admission (n=170).

Problems developed after admission	Frequency	Percent %
Sepsis	117	68.8
Hemodynamic Instability	73	42.9
Liver Impairment	12	7.1
CNS Depression	6	3.5

Figure 5. Use of nephrotoxic medication among participants (n=170).

INCIDENCE AND MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY

The frequency of AKI among participants was 66.5% (113/170) (Figure 7). More than half (55.9%) presented with high serum creatinine levels at admission (Figure 6). Among AKI patients, 69% required Renal Replacement Therapy (RRT), while 31% were managed conservatively (Figure 8). All patients on RRT received more than three sessions. Of those, 51.3% underwent Continuous Renal Replacement Therapy (CRRT) and 48.7% conventional hemodialysis (Figure 10). Vasopressors were used in 36.3% of AKI patients (Figure 9).

Figure 6. Distribution of participants according to serum creatinine level at admission (n=170).

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Figure 7. Occurrence of Acute Kidney Injury among participants (n=170).

Figure 8. Treatment modalities for patients with AKI (n=113).

Figure 9. Use of vasopressors among patients with AKI (n=113).

Figure 10. Modality of Renal Replacement Therapy (n=78).

RISK FACTORS AND PREDICTORS OF AKI

Cross-tabulation analysis revealed significant associations between the occurrence of AKI and sepsis (82.3% in AKI vs. 42.1% in non_AKI, $p=0.001$) and hemodynamic instability (59.3% vs. 10.5%, $p<0.001$) (Table 4). Age, gender, and use of nephrotoxic drugs did not show statistically significant associations.

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Table 4. Relation between relevant clinical factors and the occurrence of AKI (n=170)

Factor	AKI (Yes) n=113	AKI (No) n=57	p-value
Age ≥ 60 years	78 (69.0%)	35 (61.4%)	0.296
Male Gender	74 (65.5%)	33 (57.9%)	0.333
Sepsis	93 (82.3%)	24 (42.1%)	0.001
Hemodynamic Instability	67 (59.3%)	6 (10.5%)	<0.001
Nephrotoxic Drugs	13 (11.5%)	4 (7.0%)	0.357

COMORBIDITIES AND AKI

While the frequency of AKI was higher in patients with comorbidities like hypertension, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease, these associations did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$ for all) (Table 5).

Table 5. Relation between comorbidities and the occurrence of AKI (n=170).

Comorbidity	AKI (Yes) n=113	AKI (No) n=57	p-value
Isolated Hypertension	9 (8.0%)	4 (7.0%)	0.826
Isolated Diabetes Mellitus	16 (14.2%)	6 (10.5%)	0.505
Hypertension and Diabetes	26 (23.0%)	16 (28.1%)	0.470

DISCUSSION

RISK FACTORS AND PREDICTORS

Our AKI rate (66.5%) exceeds many global reports, reflecting a critically ill cohort.[21] Sepsis and hemodynamic instability were strong predictors, aligning with global data on the central role of systemic inflammation and hypoperfusion in COVID-19 related AKI.[22,23] The high rates of mechanical ventilation and vasopressor use underscore the role of systemic insult.

RENAL REPLACEMENT THERAPY

The high RRT requirement (69%) highlights the severity of renal involvement. The near-equal split between CRRT and IHD reflects resource-driven decisions in our setting. While CRRT may offer hemodynamic benefits in unstable patients, its availability is often limited in resource-constrained environments.[24]

MORTALITY AND OUTCOMES

The stark mortality difference (57.5% vs. 31.6%) confirms AKI as a critical prognostic marker, consistent with global meta-analyses showing AKI multiplies mortality risk.[25] In low-resource settings, delayed recognition and limited RRT capacity likely exacerbate poor outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SCREENING AND MANAGEMENT

1. Early Screening: Implement daily serum creatinine and urine output monitoring in all hospitalized COVID-19 patients, especially those with sepsis or requiring ventilation.
2. Preventive Measures: Aggressively manage sepsis, optimize hemodynamics, and avoid nephrotoxins.
3. RRT Preparedness: Increase isolation-ready HD beds and staff training in both CRRT and IHD modalities.
4. Multidisciplinary Care: Integrate nephrology consultation early in the care of severe COVID-19 cases.
5. Public Health: Strengthen COVID-19 prevention to reduce the incidence of severe cases.

CONCLUSION

AKI is a frequent and deadly complication of COVID-19 in Sudan, driven predominantly by sepsis and hemodynamic instability. The high need for RRT and the associated mortality call for enhanced surveillance, early intervention, and strengthened renal care capacity. These findings should inform national guidelines and resource allocation in Sudan and similar settings.

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